

1 **NOD2 control of RISC complex-based gene regulation reconciles evolution of interferon and RNAi**
2 **interference as components of the cellular anti-viral defense system.**

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7 The question of how the interferon response, considered an antiviral signaling pathway, and the RNA
8 interference pathways evolved together is a longstanding question in biology. In lower organisms like
9 *Drosophila*, RNA interference is intact and consists of Dicer and Argonaute processing of RNAs that target
10 sequences to be silenced, but the interferon response is absent. Nevertheless, innate immune signaling
11 exists and consists of NF- κ B signaling components (Rel, Dif and Dorsal) activated following peptidoglycan
12 recognition: sensor components utilized in *Drosophila* are arguably considered to be evolutionarily
13 outmoded or otherwise evolved differently: PGLYRP proteins in mammals are not widely considered
14 significant actors in endotoxin recognition relative to NOD2 and TLR4, or the components are conserved
15 completely, like usage of RIP kinase(s), transforming growth factor kinase TAK1, inhibitor of apoptosis IAP
16 and caspase utilization downstream of the sensor. The toll-like receptor TLR4, which functions in gram
17 negative bacterial recognition in higher organisms, is conserved but it does not function at all in endotoxin
18 recognition.

19 In humans, recognition of endotoxin occurs through two separate sensors, TLR4 and the NLRP family
20 innate immune receptor NOD2. TLR4 senses lipopolysaccharide together with MD-2, while NOD2 senses
21 peptidoglycan, activating the RIP kinase RIPK2. NOD2 also possesses antiviral functions: of question
22 here, is the question of how the interferon system, endotoxin recognition and RNAi interference, a third,
23 separate and essentially anti-viral system, evolved to function in higher organisms.

24 NOD2 is a master regulator of the interferon response, including ability to control interferon regulatory
25 factors, the oligoadenylate synthase OAS system, interferon stimulated genes of the IFI, IFIT, IFITM, and
26 ISG families, pathway receptors like IFNAR alpha and beta, and the interferon pathway DNA and nucleic
27 acid sensors MDA5 (IFIH1) and STING. The existence of a molecule that connects NOD2 innate immune
28 recognition of endotoxin and components that function in the antiviral RNAi system has not been
described.

We describe here NOD2 control of a group of genes that likely function in antiviral RNA interference or the
related microRNA pathway that utilizes the RISC complex for gene regulation, likely to cooperate with
molecules that have known functions in RNAi antiviral signaling and gene silencing.

Results

We discovered activation of NRDE-2 by human NOD2 as a major transcriptional property of the human endotoxin (peptidoglycan) sensor. NRDE-2 was discovered by genetic screening in *C. Elegans* as an Argonaute family NRDE-3 homologous molecule. NOD2 control of RISC components AGO1 and DICER1 genes was modest in a human cells system that stably expressed human NOD2 compared to activation of NRDE-2.

NOD2 controlled expression of the human homologous of GW182, the TNRC6 family. TNRC6 members TNRC6B and TNRC6C were activated by NOD2 while TNRC6A was repressed.

Processing of microRNAs for miR gene signaling involves, in addition to RNA interference machinery of the RISC complex, developmental RNAs lin-28 and let-7d. We found that NOD2 could strongly activate both let-7d and lin-28a.

MicroRNA gene regulation is described to involve mRNA decay that utilized CCR4/NOT transcriptional complex components. CCR4-NOT complex components CNOT4, CNOT9 and CNOT6 were activated by NOD2.

Finally, we found that human NOD2 could activate expression of the double stranded DNA sensor, PRKRA, an enzyme described to function both in innate immune anti-viral nucleic acid sensing and in RNAi/microRNA RNA processing for gene silencing or gene regulation.

Regulation of gene expression by microRNAs and involves function of translation factors that couple processing of sequence specific targets to translational silencing, including initiation factors (eIFs); specifically, anti-viral gene regulation involving RISC components and protein kinase R (PKR) is described to require eIF2AK2. We found NOD2 could activate eIF2AK1; eIF2AK2 induction was observable but relatively weak. EIF4EB2 and eIF4E2 were also activated, along with eIF5.

Expression of human NOD2 mutant that confers risk of development of Crohn's Disease demonstrates regulation of RISC complex associated anti-viral signaling by NOD2 is a biologic function of human NOD2.

Activation of RISC associated RNAi/miR gene regulation by human NOD2 was substantially altered in cells expressing a NOD2 truncation mutant associated with genetic risk for developing IBD. We previously demonstrated that a primary transcriptional feature of primary monocytes from patients with CD is a global failure to activate the interferon signaling system.

RNAi component NRDE-2 was repressed by mutant NOD2 rather than being activated.

Cells expressing NOD2 L1007fsinsC similarly repressed the dsRNA sensor PRKRA rather than activating it.

GW182 homolog TNRC6 family members TNRC6B and TNRC6C activation was intact, but TNRC6A was aberrantly activated in cells expressing NOD2 L1007fsinsC.

mRNA decay pathway component regulation by NOD2 was also affected by NOD2 point mutation that results in a C-terminal truncation in the leucine rich region; CNOT4 and CNOT9 induction was intact but CNOT6 activation was lost.

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Molecules suggested to function in RNAi/microRNA RISC associated gene regulation based on proteomic analysis (predicted and observed).

- Dicer interactions.
- Ago interactions.
- RIG-I interactions.
- Dhx58 interactions.

Involves helicase DDX58, RIG-I, and a second helicase, Dhx58.
Eri1 interacts with the helicase complex.

Notes and Discussion

In *C. elegans*, Dicer-1 interacts with a RIG-I homolog, DRH-1, and a third molecule
Human Dicer has been described to function in RNA interference by recruiting PRKRA.

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